

Co-Design of innovative contract models for agri-environment and climate measures and the valorisation of environmental public goods

Delphi study on innovative contracts for agri-environmental payments

Report on the three rounds of the Delphi study conducted as a part of the Contracts 2.0 project

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KEY FINDINGS

1. The report presents the detailed results of a Delphi survey conducted about innovative agri-environmental and climate measures among European decision-makers, experts, NGOs and farmers. The Delphi had three consecutive rounds between March 2021 and May 2022.
2. The report presents the three rounds without contextualizing the results; a more detailed analysis of the Delphi research can be found as a public deliverable of the project: D4.3.
3. Considering the characteristics of currently typical AECM contracts, respondents highlighted the need for more flexibility, improved monitoring and control mechanisms, and better regional differentiation (i.e.g tailor-made solutions which adapt to regional specificities both in terms of the environmental and the socio-economic context). The overly complicated nature of some of the existing schemes were mentioned as a limitation, based on which some respondents argued for simplified contracts.
4. AECM is the most popular contract type combining the different elements the most popular contract would be an AECM using both result based and action based elements, with a medium long contract signed by individual farmers
5. There is almost a consensus around seeing innovative contract elements in combination with mainstream contracts as top-ups. At the same time, it is clear that respondents are afraid of an increasing bureaucracy, thus they could imagine a re-design of the current AECM administration.
6. Flexibility is a key -point in the adaptability at the EU level; more than half of the respondents think that the ideal model can be implemented at EU level if there is a possibility for regional adaptation; only a minority assumes that the ideal model cannot be implemented.
7. Respondents see ideal contract types highly beneficial: there is a consensus that those will have a positive impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, on European farmers' knowledge and attitudes towards the natural environment.
8. The impact on livelihood security and the competitiveness of farmers are seen more positively, similarly respondents suppose that ideal contracts have a positive impact on the consumption patterns and European consumers' awareness of environmental issues.
9. Respondents attribute a huge responsibility to the EU agricultural policy in the sustainability transition of the agri-food system. Its role appeared in many different policy arenas, beyond the CAP, like customs, use of pesticides, and trade agreements. The possibility of regional or national level differentiation was also frequently mentioned.
10. According to the participating decision-makers, NGO representatives, and farmers, there are three possible solutions to ensure the room for the innovative contractual elements: the pliable, the practical, and the revolutionary solutions.
11. Focusing on the challenges associated with innovative contracts (budgetary constrains, emerging transaction costs, emerging risks, knowledge and lack of expertise), our respondents expect the solution from EU/state level policy interventions.

12. There is a full consensus that AECMs have a positive impact on economic performance. There are more diverging opinions on the impact of AECMs on farmers' position in the value chain, or on climate change adaptation and mitigation opportunities.
13. In the evaluation of the impact of voluntary measures we also see a positive impact on economic criterion. There is a consensus around the beneficial impact of voluntary measures on the environment, and about their weak impact on climate change. There is a dissensus about the impact of voluntary measures on value-chain.
14. Eco-schemes also have a positive impact on farmers' livelihoods and profitability. Its impacts on environment, value chain and climate change are highly controversial. Market-based certification schemes were considered the most beneficial for the value chain, and less beneficial for climate change
15. The ideal contract received the highest scores for their impacts on the environment and climate change, but also their impacts on economic performance and value chain position were positively assessed.
16. There was not any pairs of policy instruments identified as conflicting – all of the selected measures were considered positively interlinked at least to some extent. AECMs in Pillar 1 shows the most synergies; those are somewhat synergistic with voluntary measures in Pillar 2, Eco schemes in Pillar 1, the ideal contract, and also closer to somewhat synergistic than to no impact in the case of private certification schemes.

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Table 1. Policy coherence matrix. 45

ABBREVIATIONS

AECM	Agri-environment climate measures
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CIL	Contract Innovation Lab
EU	European Union
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
PIL	Policy Innovation Lab

1. FIRST ROUND OF THE DELPHI STUDY

1.1. Background

The present chapter is about the first round of the Delphi study conducted as a part of the Contracts 2.0 research project. The aim of the Delphi study is to explore the ideas and to facilitate discussion about innovative agri-environmental contracts among policymakers, experts, NGO representatives, farmers and researchers.

We approached 120 European stakeholders at the beginning of the study on the 15th of March 2021, and 43 of them opened the questionnaire, 41 answered most of the questions. The participants represent the European regions, as we had respondents from the following countries: The Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Belgium, France, Italy, Spain, Hungary, Austria, Ireland, Denmark, Portugal, Estonia, Switzerland, Germany, Czechia, Sweden and Romania. Figure 1 presents the basic distribution of the regional and professional backgrounds and the decision-making level of the participants.

Figure 1. The background of the participants of the Delphi study. Source: own compilation based on the first round of the Delphi survey.

The report follows the structure of the questionnaire: after describing the background of the participants, and the methodological framework, it presents an analysis of the limitations of existing agri-environmental and climate schemes (AECMs). The next part of the report is an analysis based on the ratings and open-ended answers of the participants about result-based and collective contract characteristics, followed by an analysis of the value-chain and land-tenure contracts. Finally, the analysis of the ideal contract type is presented.

1.2. Methods

The first round of the Delphi survey was administered online via the Mesydel platform between the 15th of March and the 11th of April, 2021. The questionnaire included three profile questions (country of work, professional background and decision-making level where the respondent is primarily involved) and 32 research questions organized in four blocks. The first block focused on the overall assessment of current agri-environmental measures with a specific focus on their limitations (open-ended question). The second block focused on novel contractual solutions for AECMs, such as result-based and group-based contracts, including several numeric questions and one open-ended for both contract variants. The third block focused on other innovative contract types, such as value-chain and land-tenure contracts, including again numeric questions and one open-ended for both contract variants. The fourth block consisted of questions about the ideal contract, allowing respondents to build their own model by selecting among three contract types (AECM, value-chain, land-tenure) and several contract elements (e.g., result- or action-based, bilateral or group-based, short-, medium- or long term).

Numeric questions were analysed in excel with descriptive statistics. In the following sections, we introduce these descriptive statistics (means, variance) and crosstabs to present the general opinion of the respondents about result-based and collective AECMs, as well as about the value-chain and land-tenure contracts.

Open-ended questions were analysed with qualitative content analysis using the tools (creating tags and facets) offered by the Mesydel platform. First, textual responses were independently coded (tagged) using in-vivo codes by two researchers, and then the codes were compared, discussed and cleaned. Codes that explain related concepts were grouped into parent categories (facets). During the categorisation individual codes were further refined and when necessary merged or split into two to ensure that each code covers one main and coherent topic. Inter-coder reliability was achieved by continuously comparing and discussing codes (tags) and categories (facets). Explanations for each code and category were created after reaching a common agreement on the major meaning of each code and category. Altogether 80 codes (tags) and 12 categories (facets) were used to analyse the textual answers. Figure 2 shows the 12 categories and the different codes they include.

Figure 2. Codes and categories developed during the qualitative content analysis. Source: own compilation using the Mesydel platform.

1.3. Overall evaluation of current agri-environment and climate contracts: challenges and limitations

The first research question of the Delphi survey focused on the overall evaluation of currently used agri-environmental and climate measures to understand the main limitations and challenges better and discover the niches for innovative contractual approaches. The primary limitations can be grouped into five main categories.

Financial aspects were mentioned the most frequently. The insufficiency of the available budget set aside to design and manage agri-environmental schemes, and the high level of associated transaction costs create challenges at the public administration level. The amount of compensation defines the cost-benefit ratio on the farmers' side (whether it pays off to take part in a scheme or not). Whether payments are defined as a compensation (i.e., levelling off the forgone income and the increased costs) or as a reward (i.e. a payment for public goods delivery) influences the attractiveness of the scheme: while 'rewards' might be better accepted by farmers, if they are closely linked to achieved environmental impact than they can be more uncertain, than "compensatory payments."

Equally important limitations emerge due to **institutional factors**, i.e., the increased administration (lack of flexibility, bureaucracy) of the contracts, the embeddedness of existing contracts into the current institutional and legal environment and the path-dependency (resistance to change) at the institutional level, and the importance of strong political commitment to achieve change at the system level.

Knowledge-related factors also hinder the effective functioning of current AECMs, especially the lack of knowledge and robust scientific evidence, the limited availability of farm advisory services (at least in some regions), and the lack of ecological expertise and experience with novel contract types both at the farm advisory system and at farmers.

Considering the **characteristics of currently typical AECM contracts**, respondents highlighted the need for more flexibility, improved monitoring and control mechanisms, and better regional differentiation (i.e, tailor-made solutions which adapt to regional specificities both in terms of the environmental and the socio-economic context). The overly complicated nature of some of the existing schemes was mentioned as a limitation, based on which some respondents argued for simplified contracts. Some quotes also referred to contract duration as a key factor of success, highlighting that achieving real environmental impacts often needs more time than the duration of a short- or medium-term contract (so there is a time mismatch between ecological and institutional/market processes).

Farmers' awareness and motivation were less frequently addressed as limiting factors, just as ecological constraints or social aspects (e.g., the lack of trust or other social characteristics like risk aversion).

1.4. Assessing novel variations of AECM contracts: results-based and group-based payments

1.4.1. AECMs with result-based payment: "outsource risks and price the public goods"

The participants of the Delphi see result-based contracts compared to action based more effective in supporting sustainable production, but at the same time being more costly to implement, requiring a broader knowledge base, less suited to the existing institutions and the current social and cultural context. The participants agreed with all of the statements on result-based schemes, but the level of agreement and the heterogeneity of the answers are different. It is worth noting that the statement about being suited to the social and cultural context had the lowest average and the highest variance; if we have a closer look at the answers, we see that there were only six neither agree nor disagree answers, while 15 agreed and 15 disagreed with the statement, which means that the participants were divided about the topic. Figure 3 presents the average and the variance of the responses.

Figure 3. Statements on result-based and action-based elements. Average and variance of the answers (N=36) (1 – highly disagree; 3 – neither agree, nor disagree; 5 – fully agree). Source: own compilation based on the 1st round of the Delphi survey.

The open-ended question about the overall evaluation of result-based contracts was filled by 35 respondents, and missing experience was mentioned only by three of them, indicating that result-based contracts, although novel in the EU, build on a quite strong evidence base in general. This question was the richest in terms of the length and diverse aspects addressed by the textual answers (57 different codes were used during the analysis of this question from the 80 codes used altogether to analyse the whole survey). Figure 4 shows the word cloud of the codes used for the analysis of the comments on result-based contracts. The most important (most frequent) codes that describe collective contracts are ‘measurable outcomes’ (17 quotes, 66% of all mentions), ‘ecological objectives’ (10 quotes, 43% of all mentions), ‘control’ (10 quotes, 43% of all mentions), and ‘flexibility’ (10 quotes, 33% of all mentions). Although process-oriented codes, such as empowerment and involvement, were less frequent than the above-mentioned ones, they stand out as these codes are much more frequent for result-based contracts than for the other types (all of the empowerment codes and 54% of the involvement codes occurred at this question). The same applies to the codes on external factors (83% of all codes identified here) and risk (54% of all mentions occurred here).

Figure 4. Keywords emerging from the assessment of result-based contracts (the bigger size of the words indicates the higher coding frequency while colours refer to the “parent” category of the codes). Source: own compilation using the Mesydel platform.

Result-based contracts are appreciated by most respondents for being “of great value in terms of making environmental goals clear, involving farmers more actively in achieving them, building on farmers own experience, and making the link between performance and payment much clearer.” (quote no. 42.). Ecological objectives are at the core of result-based schemes, and besides their positive (and targeted) biodiversity impacts, these contracts can also have wider benefits (e.g., improved water quality or climate adaptation), although these co-benefits are difficult to measure.

Although experience is accumulating for result-based payments, it is considered a novel and innovative solution, associated with contract characteristics like clear and measurable ecological outcomes, increased flexibility for farmers, but challenging in terms of monitoring (i.e., simple but adequate indicators are of key importance) and control and advisory processes. Due to its innovative nature, the successful implementation of result-based payments requires new knowledge, learning and enhanced capacities at the level of public administration, the advisory system and the farmers as well: “(r)esult-based contracts need to be accompanied by investments in increasing the competences of all the stakeholders involved. (...) The complexity of this approach means that all stakeholders, especially the public admin, will have to go beyond their comfort zone and to this effect staff should be adequately motivated, trained and incentivized depending on the results they achieve.” (quote no. 48)

Result-based contracts put more responsibility on the farmers’ shoulders, but give them bigger flexibility and appreciation by rewarding their contributions to nature conservation. “As they have to decide on their own which management action fits the goals best, they start to invest their creativity and start to see biodiversity more as part of their farming ‘crops’.” (quote no. 1). Several quotes, like the previous one, mention that result-based schemes build on the strong involvement of farmers, and provide them autonomy, flexibility and freedom of choice in terms of how they achieve the conservation goals. This

approach has an empowering impact on farmers, improving their motivation, awareness of ecological processes, and acceptance of specific conservation goals and measures. Moreover, result-based contracts entail huge uncertainty because whether results are achieved or not depends on external factors which are beyond the control of the farmers. Increased uncertainty goes together with increased risks of failing the goals and missing the payments. In the market context, taking risks is not unfamiliar to farmers, although risk aversion might be different across countries and social groups. *“As regards the social and cultural context farmers are well used to understanding various market specifications for products and understand the concept of a higher quality product receiving a higher price in the market. Well designed results based schemes apply this principle to create markets for environment services and design systems where the product specification (i.e., quality scoring system) is understood by the farmer.”* (quote no. 46)

Among the financial aspects of result-based contracts, reward and compensation are key concepts. Quotes often highlight that rewarding farmers for their environmental performance (instead of compensating for their lost income or increased costs) is an advantage of this type which contributes to its attractiveness among farmers. Transaction costs are also mentioned frequently, although the quotes are controversial. Experts agree that setting up a result-based scheme needs large investments (i.e., defining the suitable indicators, designing the fact sheets, providing training to staff, IT infrastructure for monitoring, etc.). Some argue that transaction costs remain high in later stages as well, mainly due to challenges in monitoring and the increased demand for advisory services. Others think, in contrast, that if monitoring is largely done by farmers, the system can function with moderate transaction costs at later stages.

Result-based payments are recommended by some respondents to be used in combination with more regular approaches, i.e., action-based measures can provide a basis for safe income, and result-based payments can provide extra incentive to achieve more ambitious ecological objectives. Some respondents also acknowledge that without adequate ecological knowledge and advisory support (to enable farmers to adopt the measures to their context and capabilities), farmers might gradually shift to follow a prescribed (agreed) measure; that is, the result-based element can downgrade to a mainstream action-based element. The main added value of result-based approaches can be realized if they are applied in the right niches emerging in the interplay of ecological and institutional factors: *“(i)t needs to be used where it has the potential to add most value beyond other approaches. There are two specific situations where this is the case - first where action-based approaches become highly complex and inflexible with lots of prescription/record keeping and second where the relationship between the actions and outcomes is weak/very sensitive to small factors such as timing resulting in widespread poor delivery of outcomes.”* (quote no. 71)

1.4.2. AECMs with group-based payments: “outsource coordination and transaction costs”

The opinions about the group-based contracts seem to be more heterogeneous than in the previous contract type, as the higher variances and the averages show. There is a consensus that collective contracts more effectively support sustainable production, although they are more costly, than individual contract types. Participants see that collective contracts are not less suited to existing institutions than bilateral contracts. As Figure 5 shows, the participants had very different opinions about the necessary knowledge base and the infrastructure for a collective contract and also about its fit into the cultural and social context. As we will see in the next section, the participants discussed two of the above topics in the open-ended questions: social and financial aspects. Figure 5 presents the average and the variance of the responses.

Figure 5. Statements on the role of collective contract elements. Average and variance of the answers (N=36) (1 – highly disagree; 3 – neither agree, nor disagree; 5 – fully agree). Source: own compilation based on the 1st round of the Delphi survey.

Altogether 30 respondents filled the open question about the overall evaluation of collective contracts, and only one respondent mentioned that a lack of experience hinders the effective evaluation of collective contracts. Figure 6 shows the word cloud of the codes used for the analysis of the comments on collective contracts. The most important (most frequent) codes that describe collective contracts are ‘cooperation’ (30 quotes, 60% of all mentions), landscape-scale (9 quotes, 64% of all mentions), ‘transaction costs’ (9 quotes, 31% of all mentions), traditions (8 quotes, 67% of all mentions), trust (8 quotes, 57% of all mentions), and ecological objectives (8 quotes, 35% of all mentions).

Figure 6. Keywords emerging from the assessment of group-based contracts (the bigger size of the words indicates the higher coding frequency while colours refer to the “parent” category of the codes). Source: own compilation using the Mesydel platform.

There is a long history and existing experience with cooperation among farmers (even if not in the environmental domain), which can be a starting ground to develop group-based AECMs. In areas where land is managed as collective property (i.e., agricultural commons), farmers naturally have to work together, but in other contexts, collaboration might be more challenging: *“there’s a myth too in collective approach, more precisely that farmers are collective executors. In my knowledge, farmers do collaborate but only when there’s a business interest, not to achieve idealistic goals”* (quote no. 8). Cooperation among farmers might require increased coordination and facilitation efforts but can contribute to joint learning and increased motivation. While collective contracts might be legally challenging (see below), less structured ways of collaboration, i.e., through facilitated interactions, increased communication, or shared visioning at the landscape scale, etc., might equally be able to create synergies at the landscape level: *“in most cases effective spatial coordination can be achieved by other mechanisms without the need for legal collaboration. (...) Softer ‘group working’ involving facilitators bringing groups together without legal contracts has tended to be the model adopted”* (quote no. 71). To achieve these synergies, intermediary actors, such as a collective organization or an advisor who mediates between the public agencies and the farmers, may have a key role: *“Only when there is a strong process manager with high ecological knowledge and authority among farmers, such an approach may work”* (quote no. 8).

Most respondents agree that collective contracts can effectively deliver biodiversity-related objectives at a relatively low transaction cost if adequate ecological expertise is involved. Their biggest added value is to enable a coordinated effort at the landscape scale. Therefore, group-based contracts can be more suitable to realise geographically dispersed ecological impacts (e.g., conservation of species or habitats along a river or raising the water table level in a region) than to achieve farm-specific objectives (e.g., measures related to animal welfare). However, there are also some arguments that group-based contracts serve rather pragmatic and economic goals, instead of ecological objectives. *“I*

do observe that the idea of collectivising an ecological target among farmers does tend towards a pragmatic /economical approach rather than an ecological approach. (...) What you see next is that measures are taken in areas with the least economic relevance. This only matches sometimes with ecological potential.” (quote no. 8)

Several respondents highlighted that the current legal and institutional system is specified to bilateral contracts, and making room for collective contracts would need substantial adjustments in the public administration system. The major concerns against collective contracts emerge from their institutional and social environment: *“(w)hile from a general perspective group based contracts can generate a stronger impact than bilateral ones, they mostly depend on the quality of the group relations and the group real commitment in terms of values, principles and shared goals.”* (quote no. 48). In collective schemes, if one farmer violates the rules, the consequences (e.g., penalty payment) might be borne by the whole group of farmers, creating uncertainty and risk for the farmers. A high level of trust and existing traditions for collective action might help overcome this challenge. Otherwise, targeted contract elements are needed to regulate individual behaviour, at the expense of growing legal complexity and increased transaction costs.

Considering transaction costs, most respondents argue that group-based contracts are less expensive for the public administration than bi-lateral contracts: *“Collective contracts are for me one of the most important ways to reduce costs of transaction and, therefore, to promote result-oriented schemes.”* (quote no. 90) However, the lower level of public transaction costs is accompanied by an increase in private transaction costs, which appear mostly at the intermediary actors (the collective organization). Some quotes therefore suggest including a higher compensation for transaction costs in the AECM if the contract is signed by a group of farmers. Others recommend implementing group-based contracts on a voluntary basis, paying a basic amount for individual actions and offering a bonus payment (top-up) for the collective action.

1.5. Assessing other innovative contract types: the value-chain and the land-tenure contract

1.5.1. Value-chain contracts: “outsource control and let the market decide”

Value-chain contracts have a good reputation among the participants of this research: they agree that it can support sustainable production along the value chain and reward farmers for their environmental performance. There are more concerns that it requires a broad knowledge base and extensive infrastructure, but less worry about its suit into the current institutional, social or cultural context. Figure 7 presents the average and the variance of the responses.

Figure 7. Statements on the role of value-chain contracts. Average and variance of the answers (N=36) (1 – highly disagree; 3 – neither agree, nor disagree; 5 – fully agree). Source: own compilation based on the 1st round of the Delphi survey.

Altogether 31 respondents filled the open question about the overall evaluation of value-chain contracts, and 5 respondents mentioned a lack of experience with them in the specific context he/she is working. Figure 8 shows the word cloud of the codes used for the analysis of the comments on value-chain contracts.

Figure 8. Keywords emerging from the assessment of value-chain contracts (the bigger size of the words indicates the higher coding frequency while colours refer to the “parent” category of the codes). Source: own compilation using the Mesydel platform.

Not surprisingly, the most frequent code in this question is ‘market’ (altogether 9 quotes, 69% of all mentions). Related quotes highlight that there is a demand for sustainable food products, but there is an overload of labels, so the goals and the communication along the whole value chain should be transparent and persuasive to realize market success. Some respondents argue that value-chain contracts are better suited to shorter food supply chains, especially because large retailers are often hard to get engaged in such schemes. Market factors are strongly associated with the code ‘reward’ which

belongs to the financial aspects coding category. Respondents highlight that the higher price realized on the market is the biggest motivation for the farmer, and this approach is often more in line with farmers' business logic than AECMs. Therefore, a value-chain contract can create an extra incentive for more sustainable production: *"(i)ff it is put on top of existing AECM as providing an additional reward from markets besides the reward from policy it could work."* (quote no. 34).

Among the coding categories, 'ecological aspects' were referred to most frequently, including quotes on 'sustainable production,' 'wider benefits' and 'environmental impact.' While value-chain contracts were considered generally useful to support sustainable production, it was debated whether such a contract can effectively deliver ecological objectives. *"Value chain contracts are often as much about a marketing campaign and presenting a particular story around an issue rather than delivering environment results."* (quote no. 46) *"(it has a) high potential because the best way to motivate farmers to implement biodiversity friendly farming methods is a higher price for their products. But also a high risk of green washing, if requirements are not controlled sufficiently or not transparent enough."* (quote no. 1)

The second most frequent coding category is 'institutional aspects,' highlighting the dilemma of 'public vs. private' control over the action and the impacts. Some respondents highlighted that public funds should support only public good provisioning, but when farmers produce private (marketable) goods which are rewarded by consumers with higher prices, then the public expenditure is not appropriate. Others argued, in contrast, that public funds through AECMs are more focused on compensating farmers for their increased costs or lost revenues, and combining these sources with value-chain contracts can provide additional motivation to farmers (i.e., a mixed approach is offered). It is undoubted, however, that the role of public actors in value-chain contracts is not clear, and the specifications of the contract should be transparent about it: *"(w)hat is the role of the government within these value-chain contracts? Control on the content of the specifications, creating a level playing field between different value chains?"* (quote no. 12) Other quotes mentioned that value-chain contracts require less input from the government or public administration, since they are set up and coordinated by private actors, which distinguishes this contract type from AECMs. This is why transaction costs – at least at the public administration side – can be lower for value-chain contracts than for AECMs or land-tenure contracts.

Intermediaries - diverse actors along the value chain - are key players in value-chain contracts, as well as consumers themselves: *"to be successful, the approach must involve all relevant actors of the food chain and must be consistently implemented by all of them to avoid risk of losing the whole value by a wrong behaviour of one of the actors."* (quote no. 59). Although not mentioned frequently, some quotes argue that the design of a value-chain contract should build on knowledge co-created by these diverse actors through involvement (i.e., farmers' knowledge of production and market processes, advisory knowledge of environmental and quality aspects, and consumers' awareness of environmental impacts can be equally important). Adequate sharing of the benefits and risks among the value-chain actors is another crucial success factor that can be secured with adequate contract design.

1.5.2. Land tenure contracts: “outsource control, lower rent for long term return on natural capital”

There is a consensus among respondents that land tenure contracts can effectively support sustainable production; also the variance is low. The participants agree that it is not costly to implement it. According to the responses, there are some uncertainties around the availability of the necessary knowledge, infrastructure about suiting into the institutional, social and cultural context, but it is a general uncertainty: the number of neither agree nor disagree answers was the highest for these questions; it is also reflected in the open-ended questions as we will see in the next paragraphs.

Figure 9. Statements on the role of land tenure contracts. Average and variance of the answers (N=36) (1 – highly disagree; 3 – neither agree, nor disagree; 5 – fully agree). Source: own compilation based on the first round of the Delphi survey.

presents the average and the variance of the responses.

Figure 9. Statements on the role of land tenure contracts. Average and variance of the answers (N=36) (1 – highly disagree; 3 – neither agree, nor disagree; 5 – fully agree). Source: own compilation based on the first round of the Delphi survey.

Among the different contractual solutions we assessed in this survey, the land-tenure contract is definitely the one characterized by the highest level of uncertainty. In the overall textual evaluation of land-tenure contracts, we can see a tendency of lacking experience with this contract type: altogether, only 22 respondents filled in this question, and eight of them acknowledged in their comment that they do not have specific experience to assess the effectiveness of this contract type (see the high frequency of the ‘missing experience’ code in Figure 10 below). Figure 10 shows the word cloud of the codes used for the analysis of the comments on land-tenure contracts.

Figure 10. Keywords emerging from the assessment of land-tenure contracts (the bigger size of the words indicates the higher coding frequency while colours refer to the “parent” category of the codes). Source: own compilation using the Mesydel platform.

The most frequent coding category is the category of ‘Actors,’ where the keywords ‘owner vs. tenant’ (8 quotes altogether, accounting for all mentions throughout the survey) highlights the key contractual players, while the codes ‘national parks’ and ‘intermediaries’ refer to the fact that land-use contracts might be better suited to contexts where national parks or other intermediary actors have access (ownership) to land. Some quotes mention that land-tenure contracts are not compatible with the institutional environment – especially the land ownership structure – if it is characterized by a high proportion of private land ownership. Instead, they can work in places where a substantial amount of land is owned by the state (or nature conservation agencies like national parks), or where altruistic land owners (e.g., charities, NGOs, or private companies running excessive CSR programs) decide to lease their land - i.e., where land is more easily accessible for tenants. Some quotes suggest that because land-tenure contracts often involve third parties (besides the owner and the farmer), coordination across the different actors might be more difficult, and sometimes even lead to conflict. As one of the respondents stated: *“Again the main complexity is that you add a new agent to the discussion (the owner of the land) and coordination becomes more complex.”* (quote no. 34)

The ‘ecological aspects’ of land-tenure contracts were also relatively frequently mentioned – within this category the quotes coded as ‘wider benefits’ and ‘sustainable production’ highlight that land-tenure contracts have the potential to shift towards more sustainable agriculture, which can also lead to co-benefits (e.g., better water quality via reduced pesticide use), although the low frequency of the ‘environmental impacts’ code, or the absence of the ‘ecological objectives’ code suggest that land-tenure contracts are often not specifically targeted to achieve well-defined biodiversity goals. The duration of the contract (‘timing’) is a crucial factor to ensure its effectiveness: *“Longer contract period is very important to achieve environmental results.”* (quote no. 63)

What can make land-tenure contracts attractive to owners and farmers? Farmers’ main motivation can be the lower rent they receive as compensation for applying more environmentally friendly practices. Compared to other contract types, land-tenure contracts can create a more predictable financial environment for farmers, where uncertainty and risk related to external factors are not as significant as in the case of result-based or collective contracts. Furthermore, land-tenure contracts ensure that the tenant maintains or even enhances the natural capital of the leased land, therefore, a land-tenure contract can also directly benefit the landowner, too.

1.6. The ideal contract

After asking the opinion of participants about the different contract types and contract features, they were asked to prepare their ideal contract: to create a highly effective contractual model for their own country or region. They could choose from the three contract types: the AECM, the land-tenure, or the value-chain.

Figure 11. On preferred contract types for the ideal contract model (N=34). Source: own compilation based on the first round of the Delphi survey.

As Figure 11 shows, the AECM is far the most popular contract type, and it is worth noting that farmers and representatives of NGOs did not even choose the remaining two types, the value-chain or the land tenure contracts.

After selecting the contract type, participants were asked to select the most important contract characteristics: the elements (result-based, action-based), the length of the contract (short, medium, or long term), and the signatories of the contract (bilateral or collective). According to our results, the participants think that the contract most appealing to farmers and more effective in terms of achieving the biodiversity goals are mixed regarding the length of the contract and the payment method.

Figure 12. Characteristics of the ideal contract (N=34). Source: own compilation based on the 1st round of the Delphi survey.

Figure 12 above presenting the preferred contract elements does not show the preferred diversity of contracts. Combining the different elements, the most popular contract would be an AECM using both result-based and action-based elements, with a medium-long contract signed by individual farmers; five respondents selected these characteristics together. All other combinations had lower occurrences. If we focus on the result-based/action-based character and the signatories of the contracts, we find that mixed bilateral contracts (with medium-term and mixed length) are the most popular (10 cases), followed by result-based collective contracts (mainly long and medium-term length) (7 cases), the innovative, result-based contract element and the collective element seems to appear together, while the more cautious elements (both action-based and result-based and bilateral contracts) tend to appear together.

Figure 13. Differences in the characteristics of the ideal contract according to the respondents' background. Source: own compilation based on the first round of the Delphi survey.

According to Figure 13 above, it is clear that innovative contract elements: result-based approach and collective solutions, are more popular amongst researchers and participants with diverse professional backgrounds. More established contract elements, action-based approach and bi-lateral contracts were selected by policymakers and farmers. There seems to be a greater consensus around the length of the contracts: both policymakers and researchers prefer medium-term contracts, also among actors with diverse backgrounds, it is the most popular contract length, while farmers prefer mixed or medium-term contract length. Having a look at the textual explanations, we can have a clearer view of the ideal contract.

We also asked the participants to briefly explain the ideal contract. After coding and analysing the 18 answers, the following word cloud could be drawn (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Keywords emerging from the ideal contract types analysis. Source: own compilation using the Mesydel platform.

The deeper analysis of the codes and facets enforces what can be seen from the figure. The most important facet is the contract characteristics facet (43 codes, 39% of the codes), followed by the process facet with 16 codes (14.5% of the codes). As we asked the participants to describe the ideal contract, it is not surprising that most of the codes refer to it. Looking at the codes, we see that half of the responses mention a “mixed approach” (12 mentions, almost half of all mentions of the code among

all the answers). The advantage of the mixed contracts can be illustrated with the following quotations: *“combines certainty (payment for actions) with freedom (payment for results). Farmers could choose one or other depending on what they value most.”* (quote no 34)

The responses also discussed the role of flexibility, timing, regional differentiation and measurable outcomes of the contracts. Some participants argued that the length of the contract should be flexible: *“Flexible contract lengths but with payment premiums for longer lengths (would be useful).”* (quote no 71)

Moreover, **social aspects** and **external factors** were discussed, but less extensively, and surprisingly financial aspects and the issues around knowledge were almost neglected in the responses about the ideal contract type. A possible explanation might be that the participants became tired by the end of the questionnaire.

2. SECOND ROUND OF THE DELPHI STUDY

2.1. Background

The present chapter is about the second round of the Delphi study conducted as part of the Contracts 2.0 research project. The aim of the Delphi study is to explore the ideas and to facilitate discussion about innovative agri-environmental contracts among policymakers, experts, NGO representatives, farmers and researchers.

Respondents of the first round of the Delphi were contacted (except the ones who definitely asked us not to do so), i.e., 115 European stakeholders. Between the 15th of June and the 15th of July 2021, 33 of them opened the questionnaire and, finally, 31 answered most of the questions. The participants represent the European regions, as we had respondents from the following countries: Belgium, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Spain, Denmark, The Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Austria, Czechia, Estonia, France, Portugal, Sweden, and Switzerland. Figure 15 presents the basic distribution of the regional and professional backgrounds and the decision-making level of the participants.

Figure 15. The background of the participants of the Delphi study. Source: own compilation based on the second round of the Delphi survey. Note: “diverse:” if the respondent marked more than one profession.

2.2. Methods

The second round of the Delphi survey was administered online via the Mesydel platform between the 15th of June and the 15th of July, 2021. The questionnaire, similarly to the first round, included three profile questions (country of work, professional background and decision-making level where the respondent is mostly involved), followed by 21 research questions which were based on the major outcomes (the key consensual ideas about the ideal contract and the challenges of implementation) of the first round and organized in four blocks. The first block aimed to reveal the overall assessment of the role of different innovative contracts in the CAP. The second block focused on the most appropriate contract type and the possible impacts of an ideal contract. The first two blocks used closed questions. The third block aimed at understanding the role of the CAP, the EU agricultural policy, in implementing innovative contracts; this block, in contrast to the previous two, included two open-ended questions. The fourth block was also built on the results of the previous Delphi round and aimed at understanding how to deal with the challenges of transition to more sustainable agriculture considering transaction costs, knowledge gaps, risks of transition and novel contracts, or budgetary constraints.

Similar to the first round of the Delphi, numeric questions were analysed in excel; in this report, we present descriptive statistics (means, variance) and crosstabs to present the general opinion of the respondents on how innovative contracts can be integrated into the European agricultural policy.

Open-ended questions were analysed with qualitative content analysis using the tools (creating tags and facets) offered by the Mesydel platform. The coding is based on the previous round of the Delphi research, but new codes were added in several cases. Textual responses were coded (tagged) using in-vivo codes by two researchers independently. Codes that explain related concepts were grouped into parent categories (facets). During the categorization, individual codes were further refined and, when necessary, merged or split into two to ensure that each code covers one main and coherent topic. Inter-coder reliability was achieved by continuously comparing and discussing codes (tags) and categories (facets). Explanations for each code and category were created after reaching a common agreement on the major meaning of each code and category. Altogether 106 codes (tags) and 12 categories (facets) were created to analyse the textual answers. Figure 16 shows the 12 categories and the different codes they include.

Figure 16. The codes and categories used in the report (own compilation based on the Mesydel platform)

2.3. Overall evaluation of the ideal contract type

The first round of the Delphi survey highlighted different directions to implement novel contract types that encourage farmers for more sustainable production. Based on it we formulated three statements to summarize some of these key areas of future implementation and asked the experts and practitioners to rate the statements according to how much they agree with them. The higher the score is, the higher the level of agreement is.

Figure 17. The general assessment of novel contract types. Source: own compilation based on the second round of the Delphi survey.

Figure 17 shows that there is almost a consensus around seeing innovative contract elements in combination with mainstream contracts as top-ups; similarly to the few examples one may find in some of the European countries. At the same time, it is clear that respondents are afraid of an increasing bureaucracy, thus they could imagine a redesign of the current AECM administration. However, the experts expressed that AECM should remain the major form of farmers' support to shift towards more sustainable agriculture. Respondents having their background in research or the non-governmental sector seemed to agree more with the statements; their scores are higher than the scores of policy-makers; while the score of the farmers seems to be the lowest.

In the first round of the Delphi, the respondents had the possibility to create the ideal contract type. It turned out that the AECM is far the most popular contract type and, as we showed in the previous chapter of this report, farmers and representatives of NGOs chose neither the value-chain nor the land tenure contract type. Regarding the contract characteristics, like length of the contract, and collective or bilateral character of the contract, the choice of the respondents from the previous round is more heterogeneous. Although action-based contracts were a bit less popular, result-based and mixed contracts were equally mentioned as a characteristic feature of the ideal contract. Considering that the ideal contract is medium long, and according to the first (previous) round half of the respondents would prefer a bilateral and half of them a collective contract, we developed three ideal contract types, and asked the experts and practitioners to choose the prototype most suitable in their regional/national context. The three options were the following:

1. A mixed contract combining action-based and result-based elements, signed bi-laterally between farmers and funding agencies for a medium duration (5–7 years).
2. A result-based contract, signed between a group of farmers (collective) and the funding agency, with flexible duration (from short to medium or long term).
3. A value-chain contract, signed between farmers and other actors of the value chain (e.g., food processors, retailers, certifiers), which builds on an existing AECM contract and provides a price premium for more sustainable products.

They also had the possibility to suggest a different alternative and explain their choice.

Figure 18. The suitability of the ideal contract type in the regional/national context. Source: own compilation based on the second round of the Delphi survey.

In line with the statements in Figure 17, also in Figure 18, we can see that a medium-term, bi-laterally signed mixed contract type combining action-based and result-based elements seems to be the most popular ideal contract (14 experts choose it), while a collective result-based contract, with flexible duration, seems to be the least popular (chosen by three experts).

It is worth noting that seven respondents would prefer something different. Analysing their responses, we found that they would prefer a mixed contract either with an option to be signed by a collective of farmers, or definitely signed by a collective of farmers: *“A mixed contract combining action-based and result-based elements, between a group of farmers (collective) and the funding agency, with medium duration.”* (quote no 6&98)

Other respondents suggested opening up more space for flexibility: *“Option A (mixed approach) with an additional incentive effect for those farmers whose commitment is part of a larger one at collective and/or value-chain levels. Flexible duration.”* (quote no 48)

We also asked the respondents about the possibility of implementing the ideal model at the European level.

Figure 19. Implementation of the ideal contract type at EU level. Source: own compilation based on the 2nd round of the Delphi survey.

Flexibility is a key point also in the adaptability at the EU level, as Figure 19 shows. More than half of the respondents think that the ideal model can be implemented at the EU level if there is a possibility for regional adaptation; only three of them think that the ideal model cannot be implemented, and eight assume that it can be implemented even without further flexibility.

In the next section, we asked the respondents to rate how the ideal contract type effect different areas. We asked them about the impacts on biodiversity, livelihood security, farmers' knowledge, and consumption patterns of European consumers. The respondents could use a scale from one to five, where five means significantly positive, three means no impact, and one means significantly negative.

Figure 20. Expected impact of innovative contract elements. Source: own compilation based on the second round of the Delphi survey.

According to Figure 20, respondents see ideal contract types as highly beneficial: there is a consensus that those will have a positive impact on the different areas analysed. Twenty-eight respondents valued the impact of the ideal contract type on biodiversity and ecosystem services positively. Similarly, 29 valued its impact positively on European farmers' knowledge and attitudes related to the natural environment.

The impact on livelihood security and competitiveness of farmers is seen more positively, but the overall number of respondents is lower: only 23 respondents answered the question. Moreover, the impact on consumption patterns and European consumers' awareness of environmental issues is positively evaluated (the majority gave a significantly positive evaluation), but around one-third of the respondents did not answer this question.

There are minor differences among the answers according to the professional background of the respondents: farmers and policymakers seem to be less confident about the positive impacts of the ideal contract type than researchers are, but the differences are minimal. Regional differences or decision-making levels also do not seem to be connected to the expected impacts of the innovative contract elements.

2.4. Policy framework for the new contractual models

In the second part of the questionnaire, we aimed to reveal the different views of the participants on the role of the EU in agriculture policy. The agricultural policy of the European Union historically plays an important role in coordinating, controlling and financially supporting farmers across Europe. We asked the participants about the ideal role of EU agricultural policy in the sustainability transition of the agri-food system, namely, whether the CAP / Farm to Fork Strategy should continue to provide a general strategy and policy framework? Whether EU-level decisions should be more strictly followed at the country level? Or rather, should countries and regions be given more flexibility and freedom to develop their own solutions and nurture bottom-up initiatives of farmers and other land users?

Figure 21 shows codes in a word cloud and the frequency of the codes from the analysis of the responses to the open-ended question about the ideal role of the EU in the sustainability transition of the agri-food system.

Figure 21. The role of the EU in agricultural policy. Source: own compilation using the Mesydel platform.

Not surprisingly, the respondents see a huge responsibility of the EU in the analysed question. Its role appeared in many different policy arenas, besides the CAP, like customs, use of pesticides, and trade agreements. There was a reference to the EU, or it was mentioned in almost all of the responses; thus we decided not to use it as a code in the analysis. The possibility of regional or national level differentiation was also frequently mentioned, as the above figure shows: 15 and 10 times: *“The CAP should provide a general framework and should give more flexibility and freedom for developing the most suitable solutions in the member states, but must also ensure a level playing field for MS’s; its role of region, nation.”* (quote no 37)

Respondents frequently emphasize the importance of flexibility also related to this question: “At the same time, member states should account with enough flexibility to design intervention to achieved this common objectives considering the own national context, strengths and barriers.” (quote no 89)

“Standardisation strategy” appears as a task for the EU-level (centralized) decision-making, which has to ensure similar rules and basic standards for all member countries:

2.4.1. Room for novel contractual elements in the CAP

The second round of the Delphi also tried to explore the opinion of the experts and practitioners about the proper place of the novel contractual elements within the CAP. Respondents could choose one or more of the following schemes as a proper room for the innovative contracts:

- Basic payments in Pillar 1
- Redistribute payments in Pillar 1
- Eco-schemes in Pillar 1
- Voluntary interventions in Pillar 1 (i.e., young farmer support, coupled support, sectoral interventions)
- Agri-environment and climate measures in Pillar 2
- Young farmers support in Pillar 2
- Risk management in Pillar 2
- Voluntary interventions in Pillar 2 related to ecological constraints
- Voluntary interventions in Pillar 2 related to investments, knowledge exchange and cooperation

Figure 22. CAP elements creating room for new contractual solutions. Source: own compilation based on the second round of the Delphi survey.

The place of new contract elements is highly disputed, as Figure 22 shows. Different measures in Pillar 2 were mentioned most frequently, 49 times altogether. Measures in Pilar 1 were less frequently mentioned (22 times).

Figure 23. Explanation of the room for innovative contract elements in the CAP. Codes for the open-ended question Source: own compilation based on the second round of the Delphi survey.

Analysing the open-ended answers to the explanation, we found that institutional questions are mentioned most frequently, followed by contract characteristics.

According to our analysis, there are three main solutions to ensure the room for the innovative contractual elements: the pliable, the practical, and the revolutionary solutions.

The pliable solution aims at finding the room in the easiest and most convenient way: „*Novel contracts need the space where they fit in. (...) For this reason new fields like young farmers and knowledge are the right place.*” (quote no 103)

The most practical solution, which is the most frequent at the same time, suggests defining the place of typical practice-based contract models in Pillar 1. Also, the compensations and/or rewards for other innovations (e.g., links to value chain) could be in Pillar 1 voluntary interventions, while allocating resources for result-based top-ups in Pillar 2: “*The suitable room to create novel contractual solutions are the Agri-environment and climate measures in Pillar 2, given their voluntary and contractual nature for 5-7 years, but other voluntary interventions in Pillar 1 (coupled support, sectoral interventions) and Pillar 2 (ecological constraints; investments, Knowledge exchange and cooperation) can or should even be associated to help and contribute to better environmental results of new contracts.*” (quote no 63)

The revolutionary solution argues for a complete redesign of the CAP: „*It doesn't make sense to get reinforced conditionality (...), good ecoschemes and agri-environment measures without a proper redesign of basic payments and the removal of perverse subsidies for people, climate and nature (prohibition of pesticides, levies ...).*” (quote no 89) or: “*The new elements of the CAP (especially the Ecoschemes but the agri-environment and climate measures also) are not suitable for the new, result-based contracts. New regulation is needed.*” (quote no 40)

2.5. Key challenges

In the last part of the Delphi, we aimed to reveal the ideas of the decision-makers, farmers, NGO representatives about the possible challenges, and how they see the possible solutions to these challenges. We asked them about budgetary constraints, emerging transaction costs, emerging risks and, finally, knowledge and lack of expertise.

Figure 24. How to overcome budgetary constraints. Source: own compilation based on the 2nd round of the Delphi survey.

As Figure 24 shows, the solution to the challenges is expected from EU/state-level policy interventions. According to the respondents, budgetary constraints could be handled by increasing the overall amount of green payments in the next CAP and by including innovative contracts in Pilar 1 and 2; it was mentioned 29 times. Despite this solution's popularity, private funds were only named 11 times. Introducing biodiversity taxing or offsetting policies seems to be slightly more popular, with 12 mentions. Complementing EU funds from the national budget was mentioned only by three respondents.

Figure 25. How to manage emerging transaction costs. Source: own compilation based on the second round of the Delphi survey.

Our research shows (see Figure 25) that only three respondents think new contracts will not lead to higher transaction costs. Furthermore, in the case of emerging transaction costs, respondents see that public institutions have an important role in reducing them, and farmers have to be compensated (18 choices). It was mentioned nine times that transaction costs should be shared among the actors, and complexity should be reduced to keep transaction costs lower.

Further suggestion mentioned that there could be a differentiation according to farm size and also according to the life cycle of the contract: there are more transaction costs in the first years than in the following ones.

Figure 26. How to manage risks related to achieving positive environmental impacts. Source: own compilation using the Mesydel platform.

According to Figure 26 emerging risks should be handled by fixed payments (22) and vis major budget (10), instead of private insurance or farmers' own strategy (4 mentions).

One of the respondents suggested the following: *“Indicators which create payments to farmers need to be chosen in a way that external factors do not influence them. E.g. instead of paying farmers for having specific bird species on their land it might be better to pay them for providing specific habitat features that are needed by this bird species. In cases of vis major farmers should still get their payments.”* (quote no 1)

In other words, the careful selection of indicators and clear rules in cases of unexpected events could also help reducing uncertainties.

Figure 27. How to overcome knowledge gaps and missing experience. Source: own compilation using the Mesydel platform.

According to the respondents, formal education (25), peer-to-peer learning (23) and public advisory (18) could fill in knowledge gaps and missing expertise (see Figure 27).

Based on the second round of the Delphi research, we have a clearer view of the possible place(s) of the innovative contracts in the new CAP architecture; about the dissent and consensus around its possible impacts and challenges. In the third and final round of the Delphi, we aim to better understand the policy coherence, which is one of the key issues according to the previous two rounds. In this next round we collect more detailed information about the impacts of different agri-environmental policy instruments, such as the eco-schemes, agri-environmental and climate measures. Finally, we ask the respondents to reveal the potential synergies and controversies between these policy instruments and an innovative contract prototype built from the results of the previous rounds.

3. THIRD ROUND OF THE DELPHI STUDY

3.1. Background

The present chapter is about the third round of the Delphi study conducted as a part of the Contracts 2.0 research project. The aim of the Delphi study is to explore the ideas and to facilitate discussion about innovative agri-environmental contracts among policymakers, experts, NGO representatives, farmers and researchers.

We approached again the respondents of the Delphi survey, altogether 114 European stakeholders, between the 15th of November and the 20th of December 2021. Twenty-nine of them opened the questionnaire and finally, 23 respondents answered most of the questions. The participants represent the four major European regions, as we had respondents from the following countries: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the UK. Figure 28 presents the basic distribution of the regional and professional background and the decision-making scale, which was the most relevant for the participants.

Figure 28. The background of the participants of the Delphi study. Source: own compilation based on the 3rd round of the Delphi survey.

3.2. Methods

The third round of the Delphi survey was administered online via the Mesydel platform between the 15th of November and the 20th of December, 2021. As this was the final round of the Delphi study, we built on the results of the previous two rounds and focused this last round on policy coherence, especially on the potential synergies and redundancies or conflicts between different CAP measures and novel contracts. In the first part of the survey, we asked respondents' opinions about the (actual or potential) impacts of different agri-environmental policy instruments, such as the eco-schemes in Pillar 1, agri-environmental and climate measures in Pillar 2, voluntary interventions in Pillar 2, market-

based certification schemes (beyond the CAP), and an ideal contract prototype synthesized from the previous two rounds of the Delphi. Each of these policy instruments were scored on a 5-item scale along with four different criteria: economic impacts (incl. the impact on the livelihood security and competitiveness of farmers), environmental impacts (incl. the impacts on water, soil, natural habitats and protected species), value chain impacts (incl. the impacts on farmers' position in the food value chain, as well as the impact on the provision of better quality and healthier food), and climate impacts (incl. the impact on the mitigation and adaptation measures taken up by farmers). In addition to the scoring, respondents could also provide a narrative evaluation for each policy instrument to explain their scoring. The second part of the survey asked respondents to highlight potential synergies and controversies among these policy instruments. Each policy instrument was paired with all the others and respondents were asked to score the relationship within these dyads from highly conflicting (-2) through neutral (0) to highly synergistic (+2). Here again, respondents could provide a narrative evaluation to explain their scores. All quantitative data was analysed by simple descriptive statistics (means and standard deviation) in Excel, while the qualitative answers were coded and categorized within the Mesydel platform.

3.3. Assessing the impacts of different policy instruments

In the following, we present the impact of the AECMs, the voluntary measures in Pillar 2, the eco-schemes, the market-based certification schemes, and the ideal contract prototype on the above-presented areas (economies of farming, environment, value chains and climate change adaptation). We also present the analysis of responses to the open-ended questions, although these are much shorter than in the previous rounds of the Delphi survey.

We transformed the 5-item scale (highly disagree – disagree – neutral – agree – highly agree) into a grading from -2 to +2. The following figures present the average of the responses and the standard deviations. The response rate was fairly high: it varies between 74–100%; the exact numbers are shown in the figure captions.

According to the respondents, AECMs have an overall positive impact on all the assessed criteria (figure below). AECMs in Pillar 1 have the most positive impact on the environment, while the least but still positive impact on the value chains.

Figure 29. Assessing the impacts of agri-environmental and climate measures in the CAP pillar 2. Source: own compilation based on the third round of the Delphi survey. (N=22)

There is full consensus that AECMs have a positive impact on economic performance of the farmers, and also the standard deviation of the answers is the lowest in that case. In the case of the other three criteria, we can see that there are more diverging opinions; some of the respondents argue that AECMs have a negative impact on farmers' position in the value chain, or on climate change adaptation and mitigation opportunities (see Figure 29).

Analysing the responses to the open-ended questions, we found that environmental impacts and ecological objectives are among the most frequently used codes. Analysing these codes in context, we see that respondents find them insufficient to reach desirable impacts: *"The general action-based approach to AECM (...) has limited additional benefits to biodiversity, natural resources and climate action due to the generic nature of the actions."* (quote no 46)

Other respondents emphasize that AECMs should follow the changes in agricultural practice: *"During time some of the requirements/measures of AECMs change quite elementary for farmers and can be moved to the requirements of conditionality (e.g preserving landscape elements, crop rotation etc.)."* (quote no 35)

Some respondents emphasized that the impact of the AECMs is very much dependent on the member states' individual policies.

In the evaluation of the impact of voluntary measures (see Figure 30 below), we see that the economic criterion received the highest scores, but at the same time, this criterion is the most controversial: the standard deviation is the highest in this case. There is a consensus around the beneficial impact of voluntary measures on the environment, and about their weak impact on climate change; no one gave neither +2, nor -2, and both the average and the standard deviation is low. On the other hand, there is dissent about the impact of voluntary measures on the value-chain, as the relatively high standard deviation shows. High standard deviation, however, might also be traced back to the fact that there

are several diverse policy instruments within the Pillar 2 voluntary measures, and scores might have differed because respondents focused on different aspects of the voluntary measures.

Figure 30. Assessing the impacts of CAP Pillar 2 Voluntary measures. Source: own compilation based on the third round of the Delphi survey. (N=21)

Analysing the open-ended questions, we found that respondents have concerns about the impacts of voluntary measures, as the following quotation also shows: *“Voluntary interventions also lead to rebound effects as farmers are enlarging their livestock while introducing adaptations on stables for ammonia emission and climate mitigation.”* (quote no 11)

There are three codes for indirect effects out of 14 codes (as we mentioned above the length of the texts is much shorter than in the previous rounds.). Environmental impacts appear three times, again in a negative context.

According to our respondents, eco-schemes also have a positive impact on farmers’ livelihoods and profitability, without any negative scores given to this criterion (Figure 31 below). On the other hand, the environmental, value chain and climate change impacts of eco-schemes are highly controversial, as the high standard deviation shows.

Figure 31. Assessing the expected impacts of newly established eco-schemes in CAP Pillar 1. Source: own compilation based on the third round of the Delphi survey.

The impact on the value chain is anyway very low, there were 11 responses saying that it has no or negative impact, and no one scored it to highly positive impact. The overall assessment of the impact of eco-schemes on climate change is better, but the standard deviation, which shows the level of consensus around the criteria, is almost 1. In sum, it seems that the eco-schemes are considered beneficial mainly for the economic performance of the farmers and for the climate and environment to a lesser extent.

The responses to the open-ended question show that eco-schemes are seen more critically than AECMs. The code environmental impact appears four times, in a negative or at least dubious context, saying that the design of the contract will hugely affect their real impact. Consequently, the code design appears three times.

“There is strong pressure from farmers’ organizations for Eco-schemes in Pillar 1 to continue to support the income of some sectors, rebalancing the convergence of base payments. As they are annual aids, I don’t think they will have a major impact on biodiversity and in the food value chain. The biggest impact could be on climate change mitigation and adaptation, because they are being built to obtain positive results in this area.” (quote no 63)

Market-based certification schemes were considered the most beneficial for the value chain, and less beneficial for climate change (Figure 32 below). However, the dissent around it is considerable (standard deviation is 0.89 and 0.71).

Figure 32. Assessing the impacts of market-based certification schemes. Source: own compilation based on the third round of the Delphi survey. (N=19)

The impact of market-based certification schemes is relatively high on economic and environmental criteria as well. The respondents used the open-ended questions to argue for stronger and more acknowledged labels, and for policies which help the owners of the labels to achieve the above-mentioned goals.

The ideal contract received the highest scores for its impacts on the environment and climate change, but also their impacts on economic performance and value chain position were positively assessed (Figure 33 below). Negative assessments are rare (only once per criteria, except for the environmental impact, with no negative score). Also, the relatively low standard deviation shows a consensus around the impact of the ideal prototype.

Figure 33. Assessing the impacts of the ideal contract prototype. Source: own compilation based on the 3rd round of the Delphi survey. (N=21)

When comparing all five policy instruments along with the four assessment criteria, we can see that all measures were assessed rather positively (or neutral), but none of them were considered to have considerable negative impacts (Figure 34 below). On average, the least positive impacts were attributed to the eco-schemes, and the highest positive impacts were attributed to the ideal contract types. We can also see that there is no silver bullet; there is no measure being equally perfect for each of the analysed impact criteria.

Figure 34. Comparing the five different policy instruments along with their expected economic, environmental, value chain and climate change impacts. Source: own compilation based on the third round of the Delphi survey. (N=19-22)

There is no considerable difference in the policy instruments' impacts on farmers' livelihoods and profitability, but the other three criteria show well the perceived strengths and weaknesses of the measures. We can see that farmers' position in the value chain can be supported the most through market-based schemes, positive environmental impacts are attributed mostly to the ideal contract type and to AECMs, while benefits for climate change adaptation and mitigation are expected primarily from the ideal contract prototype and to a lesser extent from the eco-schemes. This highlights that implementing novel contracts within different existing measures might reach different outcomes: if novel contracts are implemented within AECMs (or eco-schemes), environmental (and climate change) benefits might be increased, while if they are implemented within market-based certification schemes, value-chain related benefits might also be realised, besides the environmental and climate impacts.

3.4. Policy coherence analysis

In the second part of the questionnaire, we asked the respondents to compare the above-listed policy instruments and to assess how much they are in coherence or in conflict with each other. The rating could vary from highly synergistic (+2), somewhat synergistic (+1), not impacting each other (0), redundant (unnecessarily duplicating structures and/or processes) (-0.2) to somewhat conflicting (-1) and highly conflicting (-2). Based on the individual ratings, a policy coherence matrix was prepared as the main outcome to highlight the conflicting and the synergistic elements within the current policy framework.

Table 1 combines the results of the first and the second part of the survey and visualizes the relationship between the policy instruments selected for analysis in this survey.

Table 1. Policy coherence matrix. The first numbers in the cells show the average values (ranging between -2 (negative impact / highly conflicting) to +2 (positive impact / highly synergistic), while the second numbers in brackets show the standard deviation. The darker the cells, the more positive the impact, or the more synergistic the relationship. Source: own compilation based on the 3rd round of the Delphi survey (N=17)

Different types of measures / contracts	Impact on...				Synergies between...				
	Livelihood security	Biodiversity and natural resources	Farmers' position in the value chain & provision of food	Climate change mitigation and adaptation	AECMs in Pillar 2	Voluntary measures in Pillar 2	Eco schemes in Pillar 1	Certification	Ideal/prototype contract
AECMs in Pillar2	0.682 (0.700)	1.043 (0.806)	0.227 (0.734)	0.409 (0.834)		0.93	0.94	0.61	0.95
Voluntary measures in Pillar2	0.762 (0.921)	0.619 (0.653)	0.350 (0.726)	0.190 (0.663)		0.54	0.69	0.93	
Eco schemes in Pillar1	0.778 (0.711)	0.474 (1.141)	0.111 (0.875)	0.526 (0.993)		0.56	0.68		
Certification	0.762 (0.921)	0.619 (0.722)	1.000 (0.894)	0.263 (0.714)		0.60			
Ideal/prototype contract	0.650 (0.726)	1.200 (0.510)	0.579 (0.674)	1.118 (0.676)					

Surprisingly, there was not any pairs of policy instruments identified as conflicting – all of the selected measures were considered positively interlinked at least to some extent. AECMs in Pillar 1 shows the most synergies; those are somewhat synergistic with voluntary measures in Pillar 2, Eco schemes in Pillar 1, the ideal contract, and also closer to somewhat synergistic than to no impact in the case of private certification schemes. Our respondents saw voluntary measures in Pillar 2 and ideal contracts as synergistic (0.93). Contrary to it, certification (market-based labelling schemes) seems to be the least synergistic with other instruments: the average is between 0.56–0.69. The least synergy was seen between voluntary measures in Pillar 2 and eco-schemes in Pillar 1. The synergy of the ideal contract and certification and eco schemes are seen moderate (0.60–0.68).

Our respondents emphasize that the final design of the CAP and the novel contract profoundly influence the impacts of the different measures and also the synergies and conflicts among them, as the following quotation shows:

“All of these answers finally depend on the way that any of the measures will be designed. For example, new irrigated areas supported by investments measures will be against AECMs, novel contract and even Eco-schemes objectives. And the contrary, proper investments will promote the positive impact of the other measures.” (quote no 89)

The policy coherence analysis highlighted that the ideal innovative contract prototype is the most synergistic with the current AECMs or the voluntary measures within CAP Pillar 2. Some quotes even emphasise that from a regulatory perspective, since these contracts are novel, they are better implemented among the voluntary measures as completely new policy instruments, instead of using them to improve the current measures. If we consider the different strengths of the measures in terms of their value chain, environmental and climate change impacts, we can see that implementing the novel contracts within AECMs could lead to an improved environmental (and climate change) performance (substitutional impacts), while implementing novel contracts together with market-based certification schemes could realize benefits in a wider range, as this way farmers' positions in the value chain could also be enhanced (complementary impacts). Implementing novel contracts within voluntary measures or eco-schemes seems more controversial because the benefits of voluntary measures and eco-schemes are perceived less significant (and less consensual).